

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to the University Grants Commission, New Delhi for the financial assistance.

References

1. F. E. BEAMISH, "The Analytical Chemistry of the Noble Metals, Pergamon Press, London 1966, p. 325, 331.
2. L. MEITES and R. E. COVER, *Anal. Chem.*, 1968, 40, 209.
3. O. C. SAXENA, *Microchem. J.*, 1967, 12, 609.
4. N. A. CHUGHTAI, D. N. SHARMA, J. DOLEZAL and J. ZYKA, *Mikrochim. Acta*, 1976, 1, 141.
5. H. ALFARO, J. DOLEZAL and J. ZYKA, *Chemist. Analyst.*, 1966, 55, 84.
6. E. RUZICKA, *Chem. Listy*, 1957, 51, 1814, *Chem. Abs.*, 1958, 52, 1839h.
7. O. C. SAXENA, *Microchem. J.*, 1968, 13, 120.
8. I. A. POULSEN and C. S. GARNER, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1962, 84, 2033.
9. D. A. FINE, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1969, 8, 1015.
10. R. B. DEAN and W. J. DIXON, *Anal. Chem.*, 1951, 23, 636.
11. G. G. RAO and L. S. A. DIKSHITULU, *Talanta*, 1963, 10, 295.
12. G. G. RAO and S. R. SAGI, *Talanta*, 1962, 9, 715.

Kinetics of the Enolization of Cyclohexanone and *m*-Methyl Cyclohexanone Catalysed by Amino Acids

K. J. SINGH

Department of Chemistry, Motilal Vigyan Mahavidyalaya, Bhopal

and

G. P. S. BHADORIA

Department of Post Graduate Studies and Research in Chemistry, Madhav Institute of Technology and Science, Gwalior

Manuscript received 10 April 1978, revised 1 October 1980, accepted 29 January 1981

MHALA and Singh¹ have reported the kinetics of enolization of cyclopentanone catalysed by mineral acids. Recently Mhala, Singh and Bhadoria have published their results on enolization of the above cyclic ketone catalysed by amino acids. In continuation with the above findings we present the kinetic data on the enolization of cyclohexanone and *m*-methyl cyclohexanone catalysed by amino acids with a comparative view point.

Materials and method :

The amino acids used were of A. R. variety. Analytical grade inorganic and organic chemicals were

used throughout the investigations. The method employed for the rate measurement is exactly similar to that of the previous communications^{1,2}.

Results and Discussion

Kinetics of enolization of cyclohexanone and *m*-methyl cyclohexanone (0.01 *M*) has been investigated at varying concentrations of glycine and DL alanine and β alanine. The results (Table 1) confirm a first order dependence each in glycine, and D. L. alanine and β alanine.

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF VARIATION OF AMINO ACIDS

(Amino acid) <i>M</i>	$k_1 \times 10^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$		
	β -alanine	DL-alanine	Glycine
0.40	2.570 7.943 *	1.778 5.495 *	0.98 1.67 *
0.80	7.586 16.220 *	1.5012 6.607 *	2.79 2.95 *
1.20	16.980 12.390 *	13.180 9.772	7.60 3.95 *
1.60	34.670 28.180 *	23.990 15.140 *	13.79 8.93 *

*Rate coefficient of *m*-methyl cyclohexanone at 45°.

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF VARIATION OF *m*-METHYL CYCLOHEXANONE

S. No.	(Glycine) <i>M</i>	(Substrate) <i>M</i>	Temp. 45°	
			$k_1 \times 10^3$ min^{-1}	k_1/S $\text{litre mole}^{-1} \text{ min}^{-1}$
1.	0.4	0.010	1.67	0.160
2.	0.4	0.012	1.81	0.150
3.	0.4	0.014	2.10	0.150
4.	0.4	0.016	2.50	0.156

Table 2 depicts the pseudo first order rate constants in *m*-methyl cyclohexanone which have been calculated by $\log(a-x)$, time plots. The slopes of the plots between $\log k_1$ and $\log(\text{substrate})$ have been found to be approximately unity which establish a first order dependence with substrate.

The enolization studies (glycine 1.2 *M*; substrate 0.01 *M*) have been carried out in a temperature range of 30° and the Arrhenius parameters have been calculated. The values of energy of activation,

frequency factor and the entropy of activation for cyclohexanone and *m*-methyl cyclohexanone given in Table 3 confirm the bimolecularity of the reaction³.

TABLE 3—ARRHENIUS PARAMETERE FOR THE ENOLIZATION OF CYCLOHEXANONE AND *m*-METHYL CYCLOHEXANONE

(Glycine) <i>M</i>	Cyclohexanone		$\Delta S^\ddagger$ e. u.
	E (K. cal. mole ⁻¹)	A min. ⁻¹	
1.2	22.80	2.303×10^{12}	- 4.112
1.6	20.52	8.824×10^{10}	- 10.51
2.0	20.52	1.390×10^{11}	- 9.60
	<i>m</i> -methylcyclohexanone		
1.2	19.61	7.70×10^8	- 17.83
1.6	22.80	1.15×10^{11}	- 06.66
2.0	22.80	1.13×10^{11}	- 05.14

TABLE 4—EFFECT OF DIELECTRIC CONSTANT

% of solvent (v/v)	Cyclohexanone		<i>m</i> -methyl cyclohexanone <i>k</i> , $\times 10^8$	
	(Dioxan)	Methanol	Ethanol	Dioxan
5.00	4.77 *	2.50	2.76	2.98
10.00	4.44 *	2.49	2.74	2.90
15.00	3.80 *	2.38	2.70	2.80
20.00	3.12 *	2.20	2.66	2.73
25.00	2.88 *	2.10	2.65	2.50

*Rate coefficients of cyclohexanone at 35°.

To study the solvent effect the enolization studies have been made in 0.8 *M* glycine and 0.01 *M* substrate at 35° in different methanol, ethanol and dioxane water mixtures. The lowering of rates (Table 4) with the decrease in dielectric constant of the medium indicate that the enolization of the ketones is due to dispersion of charge in the transition state since the reactive species is expected to be the conjugate acid species of the corresponding cyclic ketone. The reaction via either molecularity (uni or bi) will involve dispersion of charge in the transition state thereby lowering the rate only to a slight extent by a change over from medium of low to high ionising power.

The experimental results discussed above lead to the similar mechanism of acid catalysed enolization as given for cyclopentanone³.

The rate of enolization of cyclohexanone has been found to be higher as compared to that of cyclopentanone³ in presence of glycine. The substituent methyl in 3-methyl cyclohexanone reduces the rate of

enolization but its rate is still higher than that of cyclopentanone. The difference in reactivity of cyclopentanone and cyclohexanone may be attributed to the difference in ring strains⁴, during the enol formation, since enolization could involve in shifting of exo-double bond to the double bond in the ring demanding two carbon atoms (instead of one) to have SP² configuration. The lowering of rate in 3-methyl cyclohexanone may be due to the reduced hyperconjugation and steric hindrance offered by methyl group to the incoming water molecule to bring about the reaction bimolecularity.

References

1. M. M. MHALA and K. J. SINGH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1975, 52, 1092.
2. M. M. MHALA, K. J. SINGH and G. P. S. BHADORIA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1976, 53, 262.
3. A. A. FROST and R. G. PEARSON, "Kinetics and Mechanism", Chapter V John Wiley and Sons, Inc., (1963).
4. M. S. NEWMAN, "Steric Effects in Organic Chemistry," John Wiley and Sons, London (1956), p. 445.

Potentiometric Studies of Some Bivalent Metal Chelates of 2-Hydroxy-3-Isopropyl-6-Methylbenzaldehyde

S. S. NAIK* and (Late) M. B. KABADI

Department of Chemistry, Ramnarain Ruia College,
Matunga, Bombay-400 019

Manuscript received 20 May 1980, revised 2 February 1981,
accepted 23 February 1981

COMPLEXATION equilibria of metal complexes of UO_2^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Cd^{2+} and Co^{2+} with 2-hydroxy-3-isopropyl-6-methylbenzaldehyde(I) have been studied potentiometrically. The stability constants of these chelates were determined in 75:25 per cent (v/v) dioxane-water medium by Calvin-Bjerrum titration technique¹ at $25^\circ \pm 0.1$ maintaining ionic strength 0.1*M*. The order of the stability of chelates was $\text{UO}_2^{2+} > \text{Cu}^{2+} > \text{Zn}^{2+} > \text{Ni}^{2+} > \text{Co}^{2+} > \text{Cd}^{2+} > \text{Mg}^{2+}$.

A study of stabilities of (I) with bivalent metal ions was carried out for the first time. Garg and Pande², alone, have reported stability constants of a few bivalent metal chelates of *o*-thymolaldehyde. They³ had also discovered that *o*-thymol aldo-semicarbazone forms soluble deep coloured complexes of Fe^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , VO_2^{2+} and UO_2^{2+} and insoluble ones Ni^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Ce^{2+} and Pd^{2+} .

Present communication reports successive stability constants of complexes of (I) with various bivalent metals determined potentiometrically by using Irving-Rossotti method⁴.